

Human resources demotivation in the public sector as the basis of the development crisis in Cameroon

La démotivation des ressources humaines du secteur public comme fondement de la crise du développement au Cameroun

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Date of submission: 12/02/2022

Date of acceptance: 20/03/2022

To quote this article:

NDOH NDZIE. J (2022) «Human resources demotivation in the public sector as the basis of the development crisis in Cameroon», Revue du contrôle, de la comptabilité et de l'audit «Volume 6 : Numéro 1» pp : 23 - 47

ABSTRACT

This article examines the impact of psychological violence on socioeconomic development. A survey based on a sample of 100 people and a case study are used to confirm the existence and significance of such an impact led to the confirmation of the basic hypothesis and to possible solutions calling for the overhaul public policies for the management of human resources in the public administration. Public agents as producers of the public service are resigned victim of a certain psychological violence from the administrative hierarchy. Public agents as producers of the public service are a resigned victim of a certain psychological violence from the administrative hierarchy. Result is a demotivation of human resources in the public sector, all of which generates a crisis of sustainable development highlighting the shortcomings of a failing public service. The result is a demotivation of human resources in the public sector, all of which generates a crisis of sustainable development highlighting the shortcomings of a failing public service. It therefore seems necessary and urgent to provide solutions to solve this problem, in particular by setting up real public managerial governance with the elaboration of a national human resources strategy supported by ministerial organization charts inspired by a New Management. Public based on the effective practice of internal audit and control.

Keywords: « Psychological violence; demotivation; human resources; sustainable development; public official ».

RÉSUMÉ

Cet article a pour objet l'impact de la violence psychologique sur le développement socioéconomique. Une enquête de sondage adossée sur un échantillon de 100 personnes et une étude de cas permettant de confirmer l'existence et la significativité d'un tel impact ont abouti à la confirmation de l'hypothèse de base et à des pistes de solutions convoquant la refonte des politiques publiques de management des ressources humaines de l'administration publique. Les agents publics, producteurs du service public, sont une victime résignée d'une certaine violence psychologique exercée par la hiérarchie administrative. Il en résulte une démotivation des ressources humaines du secteur public, toute chose qui engendre une crise du développement durable mettant en exergue les carences d'une fonction publique en déliquescence. Il apparaît donc nécessaire et urgent d'apporter des solutions pour résoudre ce problème, notamment par la mise en place d'une véritable gouvernance managériale publique avec l'élaboration d'une stratégie nationale des ressources humaines appuyée par des organigrammes ministériels inspirés du Nouveau Management Public et adossés sur la pratique effective de l'audit et du contrôle internes.

Mots clés : « Violence psychologique ; démotivation ; ressources humaines; développement durable ; agent public ».

Introduction

Development efforts in Cameroon seem timid despite the enormous financial resources invested in certain sectors of sovereignty such as education and health. Indeed, the country has not yet managed to reach the minimum level of contribution from the public budget in the health (15%) and education (20%) sectors. An accusing finger is pointed at the insufficient budgetary expenditure allocated to the various development sectors (Ndoh Ndzié, 2019). However, the causes of the chronic absenteeism of public officials can be a negative factor of development. The absenteeism recrimination note was an opportunity to note the existence of a human resources management problem in Cameroon.

Public officials are very often frustrated by the deviations of line managers, to the point of being totally demotivated at work. That is the interest of thinking about the demotivation of human resources in the public sector as the basis of the development crisis in Cameroon. The personal behavior of individuals seems to replace ethical practice in the African public space in general and in Cameroon in particular. These egocentric behaviors would have become a model of transgenerational management which is regenerated by frustration. It is in this way that the development of Cameroon would be delayed by a strong influence of the negative behavior of certain public administration personnel with the emergence of oversized egos.

For this, we hypothesize that the demotivation of human resources in the public sector, resigned victims of a certain psychological violence from the hierarchy and producers of public goods, would generate a crisis of sustainable development manifested by the weakening of socio-economic indicators.

The objective of this article is to show that an approximate and/or subjective management of human resources compromises the socio-economic development of a country and that in the absence of a real human resources management policy, navigation on sight settles for negative results. Our research problem will revolve around the following question: is the demotivation of human resources in public services a foundation of the development crisis?

To examine this question, we will first present the theoretical framework of the study, before presenting its empirical framework where we will verify our hypothesis while answering the research question. The inductive approach is the one we have chosen for the purposes of this study, which will be supported by a sample survey. We will end by identifying some possible solutions to improve public policies for the management of human resources for sustainable development.

1. Literature review

Researchers generally distinguish between two types of managers: those who have a task-oriented behavior, productivity and those who have a behavior oriented towards relations between employees – where the manager is concerned about the social climate and seeks to maintain good working relationships within the team –. These two management options are the basis of the various theories of work motivation developed so far and the bureaucratic tendencies that have arisen from them. Indeed, one can distinguish the theories of the Scientific School of Work from the theories of the School of Human Relations.

1.1.Theories of the Scientific School of Labor

These theories consider that motivation is linked to a scientific organization of work. Taylor is one of the precursors of the theory of the rational organization of work. This can be identified in three areas: a) the horizontal division of labor which is the division of tasks between operators – each operator corresponds to an elementary task, in order to automate and accelerate actions; b) the vertical division of labor which is the separation between the work of execution and the intellectual work of design of the personnel like the engineers; (c) incentive pay and task control.

Here, Taylor sees work as mind-numbing and alienating. The only motivation for such work can only be money and this is the reason why incentive pay is essential, because it fights against the downtime caused by poor organization.

If workers are productive because they receive money, then motivation is probably the most important concept in the social psychology of organizations, in the sense that it has always been conceived as the engine of performance (Taylor , 1911). But motivation at work is what triggers the activity, directs it towards certain goals and prolongs it over time until the desired goal is reached (Steers and Black, 1994). Taylor's classic theory of the scientific organization of work is the one used by the vast majority of companies until a new dimension of the company arrives with the accentuation of the infinity of human needs (McGregor , 1960).

Indeed, as long as humanity exists on earth, there will be incessant needs because man is an animal that needs something. As soon as one of its needs is satisfied, another appears in its place. This process is infinite. It takes place from birth to death. Man makes a continual effort and works to satisfy his needs” (McGregor, 1960). He therefore insists on the insatiable and selfish character of man whose self-fulfillment is the main motivating factor. This Gregorian theory is therefore in opposition to the Taylorian theory of the organization of work. While

the first is based on a traditional model of hierarchical organization in the image of the army or the church, the second gives free rein to the expression of individual talent or genius, taking into account the organizational work environment.

Among the work organization theories, there is also theory Z developed by W. Ouchi. It identifies the fundamental ideas of Japan in terms of work organization (the market mechanism with the formation of a contract based on price; the bureaucratic mechanism having as its objective the creation of a hierarchical relationship by formal contract providing for control; the clan mechanism directly inspired by Japanese companies aimed at ensuring convergence between the interests of the individual and those of the company through a common culture). For this theorist, man needs to get involved in the work, therefore it is necessary to mobilize the staff and call on their creativity and their capacity for innovation.

1.2.Theories of the School of Human Relations

For the theorists of the School of Human Relations, it is the content of motivation that is interesting to study. It is in this sense that we have spoken of content theories. Thus, some have been able to show that workers work better when they are taken care of (E. Mayo). This is what he called the theory of social man. Here self-esteem and cohesion are more important for productivity than the material state of the work environment.

Another content theory is the hierarchy of needs, also called the pyramid of needs (Maslow, 1943). She advocates that motivation depends on five types of needs: a) physiological needs (to eat, dress, feed, sleep, etc.): b) security needs (to protect oneself against the various (to protect oneself against the various dangers that threaten us both physically and morally); c) the social needs of belonging to a group (feeling of belonging to a family, professional or associative group); d) the needs for esteem, respect and trust (the individual would like to be recognized as a proper entity within the groups to which he belongs); personal development needs (man needs to fulfill himself personally and to seek the best of himself).

Motivation also resides in three needs which are not innate but which can be learned: the need for achievement, the need for power, the need for affiliation (McClelland, 1961). People who have a strong need for achievement are characterized by a desire to obtain responsibilities; those with a strong need for power are characterized by a strong desire to influence others; those with a need for affiliation seek social relationships.

Alongside content theories, there are also process theories which are only interested in the functioning of motivation. This is the case of the theory of equity where an individual is

motivated when he considers that the reward (bonuses, remuneration, promotion, etc.) for his work is in line with his contribution (skills, aptitudes, etc.) (Adams, 1960). This is also the case with the theory of goal setting where motivation only depends on SMART goals (Simple, Measurable, Acceptable, Achievable, defined in Time) (Locke, 1968).

1.3. Bureaucratic theory

At the center of public service, there is the practice of bureaucracy, that is office power. From this perspective, the notion of bureaucracy is one with that of “public service”. Several researchers have experimented with bureaucracy as a form of work organization. Sociologist Max Weber applied it in Germany (1920), while Michel Crozier and consultant Octave Gélénier experimented with it in France (1960). The form of bureaucratic work organization defended by these researchers is one based on formalism and legal rules. This allows good programming and good planning of actions and service activities to be carried out. It is therefore a model centered on rationality.

However, certain sociologists of organizations such as Laurent Bélanger and Jean Mercier have highlighted the drift of bureaucratic formalism likely to lead to heaviness and rigidity in administrative action and even "a monopolization of power for the benefit of the sole interests of bureaucrats. We then speak of bureau pathology” (Wikipedia).

These two tendencies are those that fuel the debate around new public management (NPM), a set of principles and techniques for public administration reform adopted by several countries of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in the beginning of the 1980s. These include reforms on the introduction of performance management systems, increased accountability for public administrators, the introduction of market mechanisms in the public sector, the introduction of quality management techniques (Maesschalk, 2004).

This system appears far removed from the old, impersonal and collective Weberian bureaucratic model. The Cameroonian administration today suffers from a crisis of legitimacy because it is "patrimonialized", that is to say that it constitutes an instrument of domination for the benefit of the chief and a space escaping legal-rational regulation. (Mescheriakoff, 1987). There is therefore a subversion of the machine for the benefit of particular interests.

Several studies have been conducted on the impact of human resource management on business performance or the impact of strategic human resource management on innovation, but studies on the impact of human resources on the development crisis are scarce. But many

researchers agree on the fact that the question of management is acutely posed within all kinds of private, public or even social economy organizations (Plane, 2019).

Clearly, the development of the workforce and the accumulation of knowledge capital are increasingly linked to national economic prosperity (CGNTO, 2000). Indeed, this is increasingly linked to the development of the workforce and the accumulation of knowledge capital because the development of people and skills is considered to be at the heart of this process (ILO, 1999 and 2000). Many experts claim that HRD plays a vital role in the development of people and organizations and therefore in maintaining a competent and economical workforce. and economically productive (McGoldrick et al., 2002).

Human resource management (HRM) is a problem that has greatly interested researchers in the sociology of organizations. They have very often agreed on the fact that HRM, in the civil service of developing countries, faces chronic obstacles of an administrative nature such as the excessive formalism of organizational structures and their cumbersome decision-making level (Wachira, 2010). Decision makers do not yet consider it as a value creation activity but rather as a cost center (Vallemont, 1998). Indeed, the human resources management units here are less autonomous decision-making centers than administrative support and technical assistance units for the general management.

It is by noting this lack of consideration that certain studies have come to the conclusion that the HRM function remains far from the imperative of contributing to the performance of the organization which currently characterizes its positioning in European and North American companies (Pariso, 2010).

In Africa in general and in Cameroon in particular, the effectiveness of the management style of organizations is not palpable, because African companies are inspired by management models from Western theories, which justifies their failure (Bourgoin, 1984). It is in this sense that a study shows that American theories of management (enrichment of tasks to encourage motivation, participative management by objectives), adapted to Anglo-Saxon culture, are not applicable to African culture (Bourgoin , 1984). On the contrary, Scandinavian theories of management, where humanization takes the form of an increase in inter-individual social relations, correspond better to the “community” and “feminine” aspects of African societies (Bourgoin, 1984).

To test the effectiveness of human resources, some researchers on comparative public administration have established a link between management and development and have come

to the conclusion that managerial capacities are strengthened within the framework of the implementation of national development initiatives that can deliver needed, efficient and effective public services (Jreisat, 2010). Here, administration is a pillar of development, so it refers to the activities of the state that promote economic growth, strengthen human and organizational capacities and promote equality among citizens in the distribution of opportunities, income and power (Milton, 1995).

It is therefore an administration that is subject to managerial management with a more human face where those who occupy the upper echelons and who seem to have institutionalized corruption and locked their subordinates into these practices become rather caring managers (Jreisat, 2010). People who are able to push the action of the public sector contribute to sustainable development. This is the case of countries such as South Korea, Taiwan, Singapore, China, Brazil and Malaysia which have achieved sustainable development thanks to the managerial experience of the public sector (Jreisat, 2010). The performance of the public sector is therefore seen as a determining factor in achieving development (Turner et al., 2015).

We can then make the bitter observation of the scarcity in Cameroon of literature on public policies and strategies of HRM in relation to sustainable development. The consequence is the appearance of a subjective HRM recognizable by a public sector characterized by administrative heaviness, the centralization of decision-making powers in the hands of an individual. The internal control which should be done by the general inspectorates of the public services, because it is totally inactive, leads to a managerial drift of bureaucratic power. The hierarchical leader is powerful and ineffective in the face of helpless and unmotivated subordinates. However, it is established that there is a link between the success of organizations and the effectiveness of their human resources management (Simon et al., 2013).

Some researchers have instead studied the resource efficiency of organizations by emphasizing bureaucratic power. For them, this power is defined as a form of state where the administrative apparatus reigns, essentially made up of hierarchical civil servants (Alexander, 1982). The functioning of the administrative apparatus then depends on a dominant authority, that is to say of the hierarchical boss (Tessier, 1991). Showing the effectiveness of public sector HRM in terms of the state of sustainable development means attaching capital importance not only to sustainable development but also to the development of human

resources because "the current political scope of sustainable development underlines that it constitutes an issue shared by all, that each citizen is an actor in it. From this point of view, the stakeholders in the organization are no longer only the victims or the beneficiaries of managerial policies. To support the cause of sustainable development, the consumer must also eventually agree to pay the price and the employee is required to mobilize" (Bon, 2009). A study of bureaucracy and governance in Francophone West Africa concluded that public services are unproductive because civil servants lack motivation (Sardan, 2004). This assumes that the demotivation of public officials is a cause of inefficiency and non-production of the public sector where the absence of internal control and the performance of the quality of administrative work shine. Hence this conclusion:

"While wages, which are indeed derisory, in these times of globalization where goods and living standards no longer have borders, are at the heart of this dissatisfaction and remain cited in the first place, they are however not the only factors of spleen. , even disgust, of State agents. (...) the non-recognition of professional skills, constant political or patronage interventions, the absence of human resources management, contribute, among other things, to this collective disgust. And the fact of having to supplement the ends of the month with petty corruption does not contribute to this self-esteem which is nevertheless a component of all professional motivation" (Sardan, 2004).

Other research has instead shown that bureaucracy is a bad thing for public administration, because it prevents African organizations from being effective and efficient, this is the case of Togolese public companies characterized by a lack of organization, coordination, responsibility and an absence of a culture of a sense of duty (Chitou, 2013). It is agreed that in general and as far as Africa is concerned, bureaucracy is dominated by the dominant logic of unproductivity and arbitration (Sardan, 2004).

For this tendency, a public company without an ethical climate is only the ruin of the economy and development, because the absence of ethics ruins managerial performance and efficiency. Ethics here is duty in the sense of Kantian morality, that is to say what one must imperatively do or what one must refrain from doing when one is in a public service.

The lack of efficiency of the African civil service is noted in numerous studies as a consequence of the demotivation of civil servants, which itself is caused by the non-recognition of their professional skills, by favouritism, systemic corruption and the absence of objective management of human resources.

In short, the effectiveness of HRM can therefore be defined either according to an economic vision or according to an organizational vision. HRM is effective according to the economic vision when the budgets allocated by the organization have been managed effectively and efficiently. On the other hand, the HRM of an organization is considered effective and efficient when it contributes to the strategic objectives of the organization and to the achievement of its results (Huselid, 1995). It is these two visions that are defended above.

2. Demotivation of public officials in relation to socioeconomic development

In the context of this article, demotivation is a crisis or a loss of efficiency due to a lack of motivation of public service personnel. The Cameroonian public administration is then an inspiration of the Weberian bureaucratic model whose main characteristic is the centralization of power on a person who takes the name of hierarchical leader while the subordinates, subject to the control of the latter, receive the impulse from the top. . The head of the public service therefore remains an all-powerful whose deviance is likely to cause his collaborators to lose their motivation.

All the theories on the management of motivation at work postulate that there is a link between motivation and productivity. Therefore, the function of management is to influence the motivation to obtain an improvement of the results. However, these theories distinguish between two types of motivation. Extrinsic and intrinsic motivations. If the extrinsic motivations are those related to money – a factor located outside the mediation of the person – , the intrinsic motivations mainly come from the person himself – the desire to succeed in life, a strong representation of oneself in social life –. In most cases, when extrinsic motivation is lacking, we fall into demotivation. Psychologically, motivation “refers to the energy provided, so it is proactive, because it is a feeling of well-being in a work situation” (Hondeghe and Parys, 2001).

For us, motivation is the element without which decent and concerted development is impossible. In a company, it is a management strategy of a leader, because without motivation neither the staff nor the company can achieve well-being. Motivation has therefore become a focus of the management of companies and general organizations.

Adversity at work is generally the source of the demotivation of many staff who very often experience it as violence. This violence manifests itself in the form of mobbing or moral or sexual harassment (Leymann, 1996).

Violence in the form of moral or sexual harassment is established when repeated perverse facts exceed the limits of the normal exercise of hierarchical power. These facts have the purpose or effect of deteriorating working conditions likely to undermine the rights and dignity of an agent, to alter his physical or mental health or to compromise his professional future (Chamtaraud, 2004).

Some human resources management circles believe that the law would interfere in the management of companies and prevent any reaction to incompetent employees while failing to protect the real victims (Sallat, 2015).

If in some countries, the violence described in this way is sanctioned, this is not the case for others. However, sanctions must be provided (disciplinary, civil, criminal) to stop this violence, the consequences of which are direct (loss of confidence, absenteeism, permanent conflicts) or indirect (decline in production, slowdown in development, etc.). We underlined at the beginning of this work the absenteeism of the Cameroonian civil servants blamed by the high authorities.

In Cameroon, the problem of psychological violence in the workplace is not yet a major concern of national courts ruling in particular in administrative matters. However, the administrative chamber includes a civil service litigation section (Art. 9.1, Law No. 2006/016 of December 29, 2008 establishing the organization and functioning of the Supreme Court). It is even pointless. We limit ourselves to talking about the handling of conflicts between employer and employee (Anazetpouo, 2010).

However, there is no specific provision that sanctions the moral harassment of the civil servant. The Cameroonian penal code seems to be more interested in the relationship between the user of the public service and the civil servant than that which exists between the civil servant and his hierarchy.

This lack of interest in the violence of the hierarchical superior on the subordinate is also reflected in the non-existence of a reference framework for the strategic management of human resources in Cameroon. Indeed, Cameroon has not developed a human resources strategy, however, considered as the social body that accompanies production (Ondoua Biwolé, 2020).

This legal deficit supposes an absence of social rationalization of the management of human resources which implies in particular the recognition of the personnel as actors having a right to fair and equitable treatment, a right to speak as well as a right to participate in the

improvement of the public service as a key element of development. it is therefore clear that any deterioration in human relations in a public service is the opposite of appropriate practices in the management of state personnel (Beaupré et al., 2008).

The relationship between human resource management and the social responsibility associated with sustainable development has not yet been the subject of extensive reflection (Beaupré et al., 2008). This is the reason why an analysis of the literature only makes it possible to trace a few isolated studies which highlight the idea that the relationship mentioned above is based on a conception of social responsibility. Taking human resources management seriously upstream results in social progress downstream: "Human resources management helps to shape human capital in such a way that it contributes to the performance of the company" (Beaupré, 2008). Several studies have shown that companies that have made significant investments in the management of their human resources have obtained significantly higher results than those of companies that have invested much less in these resources (Le Louarn and Wills, 2001).

2.1.Methodology

The methodological approach used in this article is direct observation. It consisted in obtaining data through a survey aimed at gauging the opinion of public officials, civil servants in public administration - ministries, public hospitals, public schools, public establishments and companies - about motivation and demotivation. professionals. We decided to interview one thousand (1000) public officials through the non-probability sampling method by quotas, using as a sub-population the years of experience in the public service of the said officials, i.e. from 7 to 12 years. The said survey was carried out from April 12 to 22, 2020. The table below provides the number of public officials.

Table 1: Number of civil servants in the public administration by year of experience

Year of experience (E)	Number of public officials (N)	Percentage of public officials (%)	Quota of public officials within the sample of 100 (n)
7	150	15	15
8	220	22	22
9	160	16	16
10	150	15	15
11	200	20	20
12	120	12	12
TOTAL	1000	100	100

Source: Our observations

We wanted to ensure that the sample (n) reflects the percentage of public officials in each box of years of experience. The formula used is as follows:

$$(N/\text{total } N) \times 100\% \text{ i.e. } (150/1000) \times 100 = 15\%$$

We realized that 15% of the quota of public officials within the sample of 100 public officials have 7 years of experience; 15% also has 10 years of experience; 22% has 8 years of experience; 16% has 9 years of experience: 20% has 11 years of experience and 12% has 12 years of experience and that the sample of officials who were to be interviewed was 100.

The questions put to these public officials focused on the reasons for motivation and demotivation in their jobs.

Table 2: Survey on demotivating factors in public services

Public services Demotivating factors	Public Hospitals (PH)	Public Schools (PE)	Ministries (M)	Public Establishments and/or Enterprises (PEE)
Low salary	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Non-existent non-salary income	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Approximate professional capacities	No	No	No	No
Unsanitary toilets	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No toilets	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Occupation of homing staff	No	No	Yes	No
Defective or missing computer equipment	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Work consumables non-existent	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Lack of work	No	No	No	No
Degrading interpersonal relationships	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Lack of offices	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Capacity building non-existent	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Non-existent health insurance cover	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Lack of decent housing	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sexual harassment	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Favoritism and tribalism	No	No	Yes	Yes

Source: Our observations

This table shows that there are many demotivating factors for staff in public administration. They can thus be classified into three main categories: the first category refers to poor remuneration or the absence of benefits (low salaries, absence of extra-salary income, non-existent health insurance coverage, absence of housing); the second refers to attacks on human dignity (sexual harassment, degrading interpersonal relationships, favoritism and tribalism), the third refers to poor working conditions (lack of computer tools, non-existent work consumables, non-existent capacity building, lack of offices , unsanitary or non-existent toilets).

This table also shows that work is not lacking in public services and that it is the fact that staff remain without work that can generate demotivation for the latter. This even pushes out the problem of job descriptions in public services, which makes it possible to know exactly the work to be done by a given public official.

Public hospitals, schools and public services are the parts of public administration that bring together the three categories of demotivating factors. The same is not true when moving to the parapublic sector, especially in public establishments where satisfaction is found more or less in all fields.

There is therefore reason to say that the combination of all these financial, ethical and material factors of demotivation can only generate a non-productive official in public services. In hospitals, the demotivation of medical staff will result in an ostentatious increase in health care supply and a drop in demand, as patients turn to parallel structures such as unlicensed health centers and pharmacies. from the street. It is the same for the personnel of the ministries whose immediate consequence of the demotivation is the coinage of the services, the popularization of the administrative documents and confidentiality, the popularization of professional secret, the loss of credibility of public services and service outputs, the devaluation of the public service among families, pupils and students whose primary career choices are increasingly oriented towards the private sector opportunities.

However, human capital is the first wealth of an organization (Zghal, 2000). It should all the same be noted, to regret it, that: "The low relevance of the theory of human capital on the African field is due both to the intrinsic difficulty of its handling, and to an inadequacy of the socio-economic environment to a mobilization of this concept as it has been formulated in other contexts" (Nkuitchou, 2022). Indeed, whatever the psychological level of the employees and whatever their qualifications, they contribute to the growth and development of the country. There is therefore a strong relationship between the development of the country and the well-being of public officials. The convergence of demotivating factors being harmful for the public official who will therefore lose his motivation to work, the development of the country can only be compromised.

2.2. Results

Within 50 women interviewed, 40 women indexed sexual harassment and sexually transmitted promotion (90%) as two realities they faced in their public services. They specify that they have faced insistent advances from their superiors who offer sex in return for a

professional promotion or an official mission entitling them to money. They all felt that this state of affairs, in the event that the advances were rejected, could only give rise to difficult relations with the hierarchy. Among women, sexual harassment precedes moral harassment. They are first attacked sexually before being attacked morally. Which was to lead to demotivation.

Within 50 men questioned on the question of sexual and moral harassment, 40 men answered that they had faced moral harassment (90%). They specified that the violence of this moral harassment led them to limit their presence at the place of service and to feel useless in the service.

All of these public officials interviewed acknowledged having been in a situation of workless for a period by informal decision of the line manager. This workless is a source of professional demotivation, because you come to work every day without doing anything. At most, a daily newspaper (the press) is served to keep you occupied. However, your other colleagues complain of being overwhelmed with work, while you are unemployed. There is a frustration there that can only lead to demotivation. It should be noted that 90% of the staff questioned (men and women combined) replied that they had never handled a single file since their appointment to the position occupied. This category of staff says they have remained unoccupied to the point of losing control. This result shows that in Cameroon, public officials working in the civil service are victims of psychological violence and are therefore demotivated. This non-work affects the sectors of socio-economic development which feel it through the reduction of production inputs.

This result confirms our initial hypothesis according to which the demotivation of human resources in the public sector, resigned victims of a certain psychological violence exerted by the hierarchy and producers of public goods, would generate a crisis of sustainable development manifested by the weakening of socio-economic indicators.

2.3. Discussion

We arrived at a result which confirms that the use of human resources in the public sector is contradictory to the principles of the major theories on the organization of work that we have identified in the literature review. Indeed, whether it be the division of labor advocated by the scientific school of labor; the motivation of the worker advocated by the theory of human relations or the bureaucracy advocated by the bureaucratic theory, none of this is taken into account in the Cameroonian public service.

New public management, which has become an empty slogan, was introduced in Cameroon as in other African countries through national governance programs (NGPs) as a normative instrument that guides and defines the State's strategy in terms of economic and social development. In Cameroon, the two PNGs (2006 to 2010) which led to the establishment of an integrated computerized management system for State personnel and payroll (SYGIPES) aimed, among other things, to modernize the public service human resource management. The contribution of this important managerial governance tool is still mixed.

The SYGIPES has never succeeded in cleaning up the staff of the State, through the census of unscrupulous civil servants. The repeated censuses of civil servants, civil servants and pensioners initiated each year by the ministries of the civil service and finance reflect these mixed results .

The texts governing the Cameroonian public service, in particular Decree No. 94/199 of October 7, 1994 on the general status of the State public service and Decree No. 2000 of October 12, 2000 amending and supplementing certain provisions of Decree No. 94/199 of October 07, 1994 on the general status of the public service of the State, provide for provisions aimed at defining an ideal behavior of the public official: "The official is bound by the obligation of reserve in the exercise of its functions; the obligation of reserve consists for the civil servant in abstaining from publicly expressing his political, philosophical, religious or union opinions or from serving according to these" (Article 40, paragraphs 1 and 2). Despite all these precautions, we unfortunately see that many public officials, once appointed to positions of responsibility, ignore this legal mechanism and instead use their opinions to hold the public service hostage.

Under these conditions, all the fairer sex is the property of the chief, in defiance of article 302-1 of the Cameroonian penal code formally prohibiting sexual harassment. Within the service, single women and married women are unceremoniously coveted. They are kept at the office at late hours for "professional imperatives".

In case of resistance to the advances of the leader, the sanction is the exclusion of the person concerned. The latter no longer receives any files and is no longer associated with the administrative tasks due. The change of office also happens very quickly – you go from an office close to the chief and prestigious to another far from him and less prestigious.

In addition to the emotional and social cost of this phenomenon in the workplace, it leads to absenteeism and poor job performance. Victims may no longer be able to work at their normal

level of productivity. They are demotivated. The State thus loses human resources likely to contribute to the development of the country.

Male collaborators have the same sanctions when they are suspected of opposing the arbitrary decisions of the chief which disrupt the functioning of the service and frustrate the egos of the latter. He thus sacrifices the mission of personnel management as a categorical imperative: "Act in such a way that you treat humanity in your person and in that of others always at the same time as an end, never simply as a means" (Kant , 1997). This is the supreme condition that limits the freedom of action of all men, in order to avoid the predominance of subconscious tendencies over social tendencies (Freud, 2001).

Collaborators are thus victims of the boss's unbridled search for superpower, because "each man tends to assert his power according to a "directing fiction" (Adler, 1992). The manager can, for example, decide to prohibit the filing of any file processed by his employees at the secretariat for routing to his level, and force them to personally hand over these files to him and to wait, on the spot. , that he appreciates them. The many initials purchased for the transport of the files deposited at the secretariat are stored in the cupboards, the secretaries are idle and their only job is to remind the employees of the boss. this new rule.

Any criticism of this autocratic practice is worth dismissing the person concerned. Dozens of public officials are waiting, lined up in front of the door of the chief, who is sometimes absent. This gives him a sense of superpower over them. Having become vulnerable, the leader can then treat them as incapable, incompetent and incapable of reasoning.

The hierarchical leader then forces his subordinates to comply in defiance of their right to professional development. But its obligation is not effective because it is not recognized by its constituents because "the obligation is effective as soon as it is recognized" (Weil, 1950).

The arbitrariness being thus established as a rule and this one as an exception, we can see, in the same vein, that lateness to meetings has become a rule. Indeed, coming to business meetings half an hour late or even more has become a common practice that would give more consideration to a public official.

All these personal practices refer to a new conception of hierarchy in public administration, which escapes the legalism of the public service and is no longer defined according to the established rules of this Cameroonian public service, but rather from an arbitrary behavior generated by the boss' state of mind, his ego or his ego. Now, we know that these are attitudes

based on human selfishness, in the sense that “the self is hateful. Thus those who do not remove it and are content only to cover it, are always hateful” (Pascal, 1670).

The country's sustainable development is the main victim of the gap that is gradually widening between leaders and public service agents. The problem that arises here is that of the management of human resources in the public sector in relation to sustainable development.

The fact that many state personnel are ostracized for subjective reasons, while the state spends huge sums of money first on their training and capacity building and then on their salaries, has an impact on the development of the country.

The contribution to the development of the country of the marginalized people is subtracted from the collective effort and the salaries are paid free of charge. Which impoverishes the state. When financial services personnel are demotivated in this way, they no longer come to work, the workload increases on a few people who, as a result, rush the work to satisfy the hierarchy. The sectoral objectives set in the annual work program are no longer achieved, which leads to delays and financial losses, because the State will have to pay salaries for carrying out double work (delayed activities and new activities) .

This is how the roads that have already benefited from financing for their rehabilitation are taken over permanently; the buildings housing the public services are constructed of temporary materials, the funds dedicated to training and/or staff capacity building are devoted to holding iterative seminars to validate the reports not applicable. We finish and we start again year after year. The ultimate consequence is a vertiginous increase in development needs, but equity capital being limited, recourse to debt is then inevitable. We can then say that the development crisis comes from the demotivation of public service personnel.

The results obtained above, which reflect a demotivation of Cameroonian public officials, sufficiently explain the reasons for Cameroon's weak development. When we know that it is the staff who are driving development through their productivity and profitability in the service, we can only be pessimistic about the development of Cameroon which is based on an amorphous and atrophied staff.

Looking closely at the prism of a demotivated staff, we actually realize that upstream, bad governance is at the same time what kills public services and what impoverishes Cameroon's development ambitions by imposing "the 'talent amateurism' (Walker, 2003).

Long considered a taboo subject, psychological violence in the workplace is now considered a real problem at work. Many people suffer from it around the world. Psychological violence or internal violence “includes abusive or tyrannical behavior towards a subordinate or a peer” (ILO, 2018). According to this report, violence in the workplace has a cost, it causes an immediate and lasting breakdown in interpersonal relationships, also, it generates indirect costs such as reduced efficiency, productivity and of product quality. The example of a country like Germany shows that there can be direct and indirect economic and/or financial costs of psychological violence. At the level of companies with 1,000 employees, these costs are estimated at 168,000 dollars per year, or approximately FCFA 84,000,000. In France, the social cost of stress, another effect of psychological violence, is estimated at between 1.9 and 3 billion euros (INRS, 2010). This type of loss constitutes consequences deriving from psychological violence.

According to an English study, being happy at work improves productivity by 12% (Huffington Post, 2004). In France, the results on well-being at work show that 67% of French people are happy at work and that this average is below the world average by three (3) points (IPSOS study, May 2016).

According to another IPSOS survey carried out in June 2000, for a country like France, 30% of French employees declare that they suffer moral harassment at work. According to this same survey, three out of ten employees feel that they have already suffered moral harassment at work. The study also establishes that more than a third of French employees, or 37%, admit to having witnessed the moral harassment of a colleague. A large majority of these employees believe that bullying is multiple, repeated and systematic in the workplace.

At European level, 9% of employees, or 13 million people, claim to have been victims of bullying in 2000, compared to 8% in 1995 according to the 3rd European survey on working conditions (2002). In Finland, psychological violence reaches the rate of 15%, in Portugal it is 4%. According to this study, women seem more exposed (10%) than men (8%). The sectors of activity most affected are public administration (14%), hotels and restaurants (13%), other services (12%).

According to a Cameroonian household survey (ECAM 3, 2010), despite the actions carried out in favor of governance, the population's perception of the delivery of public services remains generally negative. Health services are credited with only 36% of positive opinions against 33% for education, 30% for the police/gendarmerie, 20% for urban infrastructure and

justice and 18% for Taxes/Customs. From this observation, Cameroon wanted to redefine the public service by setting up a standard to evaluate the services rendered in the private and public administrations, with the objective of achieving a standard that will make it possible to evaluate the quality of the services rendered in the administrations. .

This is a document drawn up in 2017 under the technical control of the National Agency for Standards and Quality (ANOR) aimed at evaluating the performance of administrations and evaluating the quality of the services provided. However, it should be concluded that each country has its own definition of public service (Tamekou, 2008). The service provided by an administration can only be of quality if those who drive this administration, from the base to the top, are motivated.

Table 3: Indicators reflecting a development crisis in Cameroon

Literal development indicator	Numerical development indicator	observations
HDI	0.563 (in 2019)	Cameroon has an average Human Development. It ranks 153rd out of 189 countries
GDP	\$39.01 billion (in 2019 i.e. 19,505 billion FCFA)	Very far behind Ivory Cost with 58.54 billion USD
Multidimensional Poverty	45,3% (the most recent IPM dates back to 2014), which represents in absolute value 11,430,000 people)	23.8% of people live below the income threshold established at 1.90 dollars (2011 Purchasing Power Parity) 950 FCFA per day
Rate of growth	03,7%	This is the growth rate recorded in 2019
Poverty rate	40%	This poverty rate is the one recorded in 2019

Source: AfDB Cameroon Economic Outlook and Human Development Report 2020, The Next Frontier: Human Development

This table shows us that Cameroon's development indicators are extremely low compared to some countries at the same level of development such as Ivory Cost. This weakness in development is explained, as we said above, by poor supervision of public officials in particular and human resources in general. As long as the Cameroonian public service has within it adventurers who have taken on responsibilities through tribalism, cronyism and

favouritism, it will always be it will always be a brake on the development of human resources and consequently on production and economic development.

Conclusion

At the end of this study, it appears that the development of a country is subject to the performance and/or production of its public officials. In Cameroon, public administration is 80% affected by the demotivation of public officials who are victims of psychological violence. That compromises the country's development efforts.

The results we obtained from the survey carried out in some public administration structures showed that development is correlated with a good performance of the productive actors who are the public officials. Good management of human resources has a highly significant impact on the country's growth. To significantly increase Cameroon's growth, it is therefore necessary to define some possible solutions for the improvement of public policies in the area of human resources.

With this in mind, the government should resolutely commit to managing the human capital of the public sector through the adoption of functional mobility. Most public officials, especially senior service officials, occupy the same appointment position on average between 15 and 25 years with the same content. This does not guarantee the efficiency of performance and economic development.

This article could therefore help decision-making spheres in Cameroon in particular and in Africa in general to commission in-depth audits and controls on the functioning of public administrations. In addition, this study will be useful for the development of a national human resources strategy, public governance being already very deficient as well as the practice of new management public and internal control.

The limits that could be observed on the statistical aspect of the study testify to the difficulty of entering into the intimate life of the public administration, where one can easily examine its traditional values, namely accountability, neutrality, justice, equity, representativeness, performance capacity, efficiency and integrity (Lemire and Gagnon, 2002). Finally, this study allows decision makers to consider in a close perspective the development of organizational charts and the adoption of an ethical code for the determination of suitable working conditions (Lefkowitz, 2006).

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